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UTILIZING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE TO ENHANCE THE COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF FUTURE VOCATIONAL DISCIPLINE TEACHERS

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ІНОЗЕМНА МОВА ЯК ІНСТРУМЕНТ ФОРМУВАННЯ КОМУНІКАТИВНОЇ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТІ МАЙБУТНІХ ВИКЛАДАЧІВ ТЕХНІЧНИХ ДИСЦИПЛІН

Abstract.

Nowadays, education is moving focus from just knowledge to "competence". This helps to address the issue in many higher education institutions where students have theoretical knowledge but struggle to apply it to solve tasks or problems. When teaching future teachers of technical foreign languages, the main aim is to develop their communication skills. This involves encouraging them to participate in oral and written exchanges with others in a foreign language. The goal is to help them become effective communicators in specific areas and language forms, using different types of communicative activities. We're discussing the enhancement of communicative competence in foreign languages for future teachers of technical disciplines. Specifically, communicative competence in a foreign language refers to the ability to effectively use language resources in various contexts, situations, criteria, and communication tasks. Consequently, language materials are viewed as tools for facilitating and engaging in meaningful communication.

Based on an analysis of theoretical material and university practice, it has been determined that the formation of foreign language professional communicative competence among technical specialists occurs through multiple stages that progress sequentially. As such, one can assert that the dynamics of developing foreign language professional communicative competence unfolds in the following pattern: starting with the development of linguistic, communicative, and socio-cultural competences, then advancing to the establishment of foreign language professional communicative competence, and finally culminating in the stage of fostering and solidifying the professionalism of future technical discipline teachers' secondary linguistic persona.

To develop the necessary skills in future specialists for a particular type of speech activity and achieve the required level of foreign language communicative competence, it is essential to prioritize providing students with active oral practice in a foreign language. Merely relying on conditional communicative tasks or classroom exercises is insufficient in forming foreign language communicative competence outside of a language-rich environment. There must also be a focus on enabling students to think, solve specific problems, and engage in discussions about the means of solving them. This approach ensures that they are concentrating on the content of their statements, while the language itself serves its primary purpose of shaping and articulating thoughts. Additionally, in order for students to perceive language as a tool for intercultural interaction, it is paramount not only to expose them to culture-specific materials, but also to employ various techniques that foster active dialogue between cultures. This way, students can gain firsthand experience of how language functions within a new culture, facilitating a deeper understanding of its nuances.

Анотація.

На основі аналізу психолого-педагогічної літератури, в статті здійснено спробу розкрити поняття «іноземна професійна комунікативна компетентність» у контексті сучасної вищої технічної освіти. Це поняття розглядається як динамічна інтегративна професійно важлива якість особистості майбутнього викладача технічних дисциплін, яка дозволяє ефективно здійснювати міжкультурні професійні контакти під час вирішення технічних завдань та комунікаційних ситуацій у сфері професійної діяльності. Автор виділяє наступні компоненти іноземної професійно-комунікативної компетентності: мотиваційно-ціннісний, що передбачає наявність ціннісного ставлення до процесу міжкультурної професійної комунікації, що виражається у бажанні підтримувати активність комунікативної професійної діяльності при вирішенні технічних завдань; пізнавальний, що включає знання іноземної мови та розуміння соціолінгвістичного і соціокультурного характеру мови для вирішення професійних комунікативних завдань; діяльнісний, що передбачає реалізацію діяльності, спрямованої на міжкультурну професійну комунікативну взаємодію з метою набуття та поповнення комунікативного досвіду; рефлексивно-оціночний, що включає самостійне оцінювання результатів комунікативної професійної діяльності та поліпшення набутих комунікативних навичок.

У статті автор виокремлює ключові компетенції (лінгвістична, комунікативна, прагматична), які складають структурно-змістовну модель іноземної професійної комунікативної компетентності майбутнього викладача технічних дисциплін; підкреслює, що цільовий, змістовий, процесуально-техно-

логічний та результативний компоненти вважаються ключовими структурними складовими моделі формування іношомовної комунікативної компетентності фахівця технічного профілю. У статті визначено умови, які сприяють формуванню іношомовної професійної комунікативної компетентності студентів під час викладання іноземної мови у вищих технічних навчальних закладах. На основі аналізу теоретичних матеріалів та практики в університетах встановлено, що процес формування цієї компетентності у фахівців технічного профілю відбувається в кілька етапів, які поступово змінюють один одного. Зазначено, що динаміка формування іношомовної професійної комунікативної компетентності проходить через наступні етапи: розвиток лінгвістичної, комунікативної та соціокультурної компетенцій, потім формування іношомовної професійної комунікативної компетентності, і, нарешті, досягнення професіоналізму у вторинної мовленнєвої особистості майбутніх викладачів технічних дисциплін.

Keywords: foreign language professional communicative competence, future teacher of vocational disciplines, competence, communication, higher educational institution, cross-cultural interaction, communicative learning.

Ключові слова: іношомовна професійна комунікативна компетентність, майбутній викладач технічних дисциплін, компетенція, комунікація, заклад вищої освіти, міжкультурна взаємодія, комунікативне навчання.

Problem statement. Globalization and integration efforts in Ukraine require the training of specialists with strong foreign language skills. These skills are essential for effective communication with people from different cultures. The analysis of teaching foreign languages to technical specialists shows that developing communication skills in a foreign language is easier when certain pedagogical principles are revised. For example, Ukraine's participation in the Bologna Process helps align national higher education systems and create a unified European market for skilled labor. Additionally, Ukrainian higher education focuses on implementing the state educational standard and considering the profile of the industry. Establishing a common European educational space needs Ukraine's higher education institutions to adopt a competence-based approach. This approach focuses on developing practical skills and the ability to apply knowledge, particularly in vocational education and foreign language learning. Establishing a common European educational space needs Ukraine's higher education institutions to adopt a competence-based approach. This approach focuses on developing practical skills and the ability to apply knowledge, particularly in vocational education and foreign language learning.

Relevance of the problem. Foreign authors such as B. Amadei, G. Bugliarello, L. Corrello, D.P. Daniels, A.L. Darling, K. McCormick, and M. Yusoff have effectively addressed this issue. They have provided studies that analyze the psychological and pedagogical aspects of forming communicative competence and the development of linguistic and mental activity. Works by P.Y. Halperin, L.K. Heichman, G.A. Kitaygorodskaya, E.S. Polat, J. Searle, and others also contribute to this important area of research.

Many scientists are interested in developing communication skills, but there is still a lack of academic knowledge and practices to fully tap into higher education's potential to develop these skills for technical specialists. Technical fields of study and humanities differ in how communication is practiced and its importance in the learning process and implementation. It is important to note that there are contradictions between several key points today: the potential prospects of the educational program designed to train future teachers

of technical disciplines in order to cultivate communicative competence, and the inadequately developed pedagogical conditions for this process; the insufficient study of communicative competence from a general psychological and pedagogical perspective, as well as the underdeveloped theoretical and practical approaches to fostering communicative competence among technical specialists; the requirements for the level of communicative competence expected of graduates from technical fields of study, which reflect their preparedness to engage in professional activities within intercultural interactions, and the discrepancy in the level of practical training of these specialists.

The purpose of the article is to reveal the essence of the concept of "foreign language professional communicative competence" in the context of modern higher vocational education based on the analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature; to identify the main competencies that make up the structural and content model of foreign language professional communicative competence of a future teacher of technical disciplines; to indicate its structural components; to determine the conditions that contribute to the formation of students' foreign language professional communicative competence in the process of teaching a foreign language in higher education.

Presentation of the basic material. Considering the significant impact of learning a foreign language on the academic preparation of a specialist, it is necessary to consider its key functions:

- Just like any other academic discipline, learning a foreign language plays a crucial role in the holistic development of a specialist. It not only broadens their horizons but also deepens their understanding of the world around them and diverse national cultures.

- The educational process intertwines with the shaping of a specialist's personality. When it comes to technical professionals, the deliberate cultivation of specific character traits, essential for their professional growth, stands out as a fundamental purpose of learning a foreign language.

- Foreign language study impacts students' intellectual activity, fostering independent work, bilingual dictionary usage, and the development of linguistics

tic self-education. It also promotes creativity and abstract thinking. Additionally, it exposes students to different thought formulations and ideas from their native language, enhancing imagination through real-life communication scenarios and language games [1, p.214].

- Learning a foreign language impacts communication and speech in the native language. It helps develop students' language abilities and speech behavior, improving proficiency.

- Communicative learning aims to model the communication process during the learning experience. Learning a foreign language, for example, can significantly enhance communication skills. In language classes, students not only learn the language itself but also acquire communication techniques, speech etiquette, and the nuances of dialogue and group communication. They become adept at addressing various communication challenges, become proficient speech partners, and develop essential skills to connect with others [2, p.48]. These abilities, such as taking initiative, displaying friendliness, and communicating correctly, are crucial qualities for a modern vocational discipline teacher.

"Foreign language professional communicative competence" refers to a person's ability to effectively communicate in a foreign language while conducting professional activities. This competence includes both the motivation and value system necessary for successful intercultural professional communication. Acquiring foreign language professional communicative competence will enable a technical specialist to effectively engage in intercultural communication as a non-native speaker; interact with foreign language speakers by incorporating advanced knowledge of technical sciences, scientific perspectives, professional nuances, national values, norms, and perspectives; foster a positive attitude during professional communication in a foreign language; employ appropriate methods of verbal and non-verbal communication based on the context.

Through an examination of scientific and pedagogical literature, we can identify the key competencies that constitute the structural and content framework of foreign language professional communicative competence [3, p.250]:

Linguistics encompasses essential skills that determine the mastery of both oral and written foreign languages. Speech competence involves possessing knowledge about the language, as well as the ability to accurately identify and utilize its different linguistic components. Linguistic competence, on the other hand, refers to the ability to use the language effectively in various communication tasks, employing linguistic tools and understanding their functioning to convey emotions and convey intricate intellectual and professional information.

The communicative aspect encompasses both professional and intercultural competencies. Professional and communicative competence entails the correct application of language and linguistic means according to communicative goals. It involves constructing speech behavior that is tailored to professional communication situations, and the ability to engage in various foreign

language activities within the technical field. Intercultural competence, on the other hand, entails having a specific knowledge base about the culture associated with a particular foreign language. Such knowledge is utilized to facilitate cultural interaction within the scientific and technical realm. Moreover, it also involves overcoming intercultural barriers during foreign language communication.

Pragmatic competency encompasses both information technology and self-educational skills crucial for a technical specialist. Information and technological competence refer to the ability to seek and acquire relevant professional information from diverse sources, translate it into different sign systems, assess its value, and effectively utilize Internet resources in professional endeavors [4, p.50]. The development of self-educational skills in a technical specialist is somewhat hindered by the limited academic hours dedicated to foreign language learning in higher education. Therefore, a key requirement for continuous self-improvement in professional performance is the capacity to expand knowledge and learn through independent research and creative endeavors in the technical domain.

The key components for developing a technical specialist's foreign language communicative competence are the target, content, procedural and technological, and result components.

The *cornerstone* of developing foreign language communicative competence for technical specialists is the formulation of clear and strategic goals, serving as the foundation for shaping the content. The process of cultivating the competencies encompassed in foreign language communicative competence should pave the way for attaining educational objectives (such as fostering professionally significant qualities and motivation to explore foreign cultures), as well as educational outcomes (including elevating the overall cultural and professional proficiency of technical specialists, and expanding and enhancing foreign language proficiency through continuous self-education). Furthermore, the process should contribute to developmental objectives (shaping the intellectual, psychological, and motivational aspects of specialists' personalities, fostering self-improvement), and personal growth.

The content component encompasses various forms of education, including formal, non-formal, and informal. Formal education consists of practical classroom lessons and didactic materials designed to develop foreign language communicative skills. Non-formal education involves active participation in international language programs, scientific conferences, competitions, quizzes, and other events. Informal education encompasses activities such as preparing for language competitions, essay writing, maintaining a student's diary, and creating a portfolio.

The procedural and technological components comprise a system of stages: stage 1 involves establishing the theoretical foundation, stage 2 focuses on acquiring knowledge at the reproduction level, and stage 3 emphasizes the transfer and independent application of acquired knowledge and skills to solve educational research problems and tasks related to informal speech activity. These components are supported by various

technologies such as games, projects, and methods implementing contextual learning and problem-based learning, which facilitate the development of specific competences through a set of actions by the participants in the educational process.

The resulting component represents the structural framework of a technical specialist's communicative competence in a foreign language, encompassing motivational, cognitive, and reflective-evaluative elements, as well as the evaluation criteria for the development of these components [5,p.124]. This includes an assessment of the individual's motivation for learning a foreign language, their comprehension of foreign language material, and the extent to which they have developed reflective skills and self-regulation abilities.

Developing students' foreign language professional competence in higher technical education involves:

- using philosophical, scientific approaches and technologies specific to teaching future technical teachers;
- applying various language teaching methods based on technical educational level;
- promoting personality-oriented learning and building tolerance, empathy, respect for culture;
- implementing competence-based approach and considering international standards;
- combining various teaching approaches;
- assessing competence level with credit-modular teaching technology;
- organizing control and self-assessment of students' performance;
- monitoring the development of professional interests and interdisciplinary integration;
- establishing personalized learning trajectories and gradual competence development.

Conclusions and prospects for further research. The main goal of education has shifted from knowledge to "competence". This change addresses a common problem in higher education: students often have theoretical knowledge, but struggle to apply it to solve real-world problems or tasks. One of the main objectives of teaching future teachers in technical disciplines a foreign language is to develop their communicative skills. This entails engaging future specialists in oral and written communication within a foreign language team, and fostering the psychophysiological mechanisms necessary for effective communication in specific areas and language forms. Put simply, the goal is to enhance the communicative competence of future

technical discipline teachers in foreign languages. This involves comparing linguistic tools with specific areas, situations, criteria, and communication tasks, recognizing language material as a means of enabling speech communication.

Based on the in-depth analysis of theoretical material and practical experience in universities, it has been established that the process of cultivating foreign language professional communicative competence in technical specialists unfolds through a series of sequential stages. Consequently, it is evident that the evolution of foreign language professional communicative competence follows the following progressive sequence: starting from the refinement of linguistic, communicative, and socio-cultural competences, advancing towards the establishment of foreign language professional communicative competence, and ultimately culminating in the growth and consolidation of expertise within the secondary linguistic persona of future technical discipline educators.

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